

Supplementary Materials: Intermolecular Interactions and In Vitro Performance of Methyl Anthranilate in Commercial Sunscreen Formulations

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1. High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)

In order to ascertain if [2+2] photocycloadditions take place in mixtures containing MA and/or EHMC, three mixtures were prepared, containing (in % w/w):

- **Mixture A:** 71% MA, 29% SCHERCEMOL™ LL
- **Mixture B:** 71% EHMC, 29% SCHERCEMOL™ LL
- **Mixture C:** 35.5% MA, 35.5% EHMC, 29% SCHERCEMOL™ LL (Trademark owned by The Lubrizol Corporation or its affiliates.)

The ingredients were simply added to a beaker and mixed together with a magnetic stirrer until the mixture was homogeneous, after which they were transferred to a glass vial. High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) measurements were then taken for each mixture before and after two hours of irradiation with a SUNTEST CPS+ (III) solar simulator (Atlas Material Testing Solutions), delivering 550 W/m² over the 300–800 nm wavelength range (the exact transparency of the glass vials to wavelengths in this range is not known).

Given the high concentration of these mixtures, 0.1 g of each mixture was diluted in ethanol (absolute, analytical grade, ExpertQ®, ACS, ISO, Reag. Ph Eur, Scharlab) to a total volume of 10 mL. These solutions were sonicated for 15 minutes and further diluted by 0.1/10 with the same solvent (ethanol). The solutions thus prepared were then analyzed by injecting 5 µL of each solution into a Shimadzu Prominence Series HPLC setup with a 5 µm, C-18 and 250 × 4.60 mm Kromasil column equipped with a PDA Detector (SPD-M20A) set at either 220 nm or 300 nm to detect any species absorbing these wavelengths. A mixture of water and methanol (HPLC gradient grade, 99.9+% CH₃OH, 0.2 µm filtrated, ChemLab) was used as the mobile phase. An 80–100% gradient elution method was employed (to a final 100% of methanol over 30 minutes) and held for 30 minutes at a flux of 1 mL/min. The resulting chromatograms are shown in Figures S1 to S6.

In all cases, i.e. for all mixtures before and after irradiation and independently of detection wavelength, no peaks corresponding to photoproducts are observed; all peaks present in the chromatograms match the peaks present in the standard HPLC curve, obtained from a non-irradiated sample containing both MA and EHMC for comparison. While this suggests no photoproducts result from the irradiation of either MA, EHMC or a combination of these two filters, the obvious color change observed after irradiation of these mixtures, particularly mixture A (see main manuscript) is evidence of the contrary. It is plausible that any potential photoproducts resulting from the irradiation of mixtures A, B and C do not absorb the wavelengths used in our HPLC measurements, and hence could not be detected.

Figure S1. Chromatogram obtained for mixture A (containing only MA) at 220 nm detection, before and after irradiation (yellow and green lines, respectively). Also shown in pink is a standard chromatogram for a sample of MA and EHMC, used for comparison, as well as the chromatogram corresponding to the solvent (black line).

Figure S2. Chromatogram obtained for mixture A (containing only MA) at 300 nm detection, before and after irradiation (yellow and green lines, respectively). Also shown in pink is a standard chromatogram for a sample of MA and EHMC, used for comparison, as well as the chromatogram corresponding to the solvent (black line).

Figure S3. Chromatogram obtained for mixture B (containing only EHMC) at 220 nm detection, before and after irradiation (yellow and green lines, respectively). Also shown in pink is a standard chromatogram for a sample of MA and EHMC, used for comparison, as well as the chromatogram corresponding to the solvent (black line).

Figure S4. Chromatogram obtained for mixture B (containing only EHMC) at 300 nm detection, before and after irradiation (yellow and green lines, respectively). Also shown in pink is a standard chromatogram for a sample of MA and EHMC, used for comparison, as well as the chromatogram corresponding to the solvent (black line).

Figure S5. Chromatogram obtained for mixture C (containing MA and EHMC) at 220 nm detection, before and after irradiation (yellow and green lines, respectively). Also shown in pink is a standard chromatogram for a sample of MA and EHMC, used for comparison, as well as the chromatogram corresponding to the solvent (black line).

Figure S6. Chromatogram obtained for mixture C (containing MA and EHMC) at 300 nm detection, before and after irradiation (yellow and green lines, respectively). Also shown in pink is a standard chromatogram for a sample of MA and EHMC, used for comparison, as well as the chromatogram corresponding to the solvent (black line).

2. Mass Spectrometry

Given the difficulty to detect any photoproducts in the HPLC chromatograms obtained with UV detection (shown above), and given that the marked color change observed upon irradiation of mixtures A, B and C (see main manuscript) strongly suggests some photochemical process has taken place, the irradiated samples were further analyzed by HPLC with mass spectrometry (MS) detection.

Diluted samples of each mixture were prepared by diluting 25 mg of each mixture in ethanol (absolute, analytical grade, ExpertQ®, ACS, ISO, Reag. Ph Eur, Scharlab), to a final solution weight of 1 g. A volume of 0.1 μ L of each of these samples was then directly injected (i.e. no column) into a Shimadzu Prominence Series HPLC setup equipped with QqQ detector (LCMS-8040), which utilizes positive electrospray ionization and scans over the 100–2000 mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) range. The mobile phase consisted of (i) water with 0.1% formic acid (eluent additive of LC-MS, Scharlab), and (ii) acetonitrile (RS GOLD for HPLC-Ultragradient, Carlo Erba Reagents) with 0.07% formic acid (eluent additive of LC-MS, Scharlab); formic acid was added here to facilitate positive ionization. An isocratic method was used,

with 80% of eluent (ii) held for one minute, resulting in a flux of 0.3 mL/min. The same procedure was followed to obtain a mass spectrum for non-irradiated SCHERCEMOL™ LL (not shown) for comparison. The mass spectra of mixtures A, B and C are shown in Figure S7, S8 and S9, respectively.

The two dominant peaks in the mass spectra of SCHERCEMOL™ LL, which are also consistently observed in the mass spectra of mixtures A, B and C, are located approximately at $m/z = 425$ and $m/z = 497$ (not shown). Coincidentally, this is also the m/z region where the trimerization photoproduct suggested by Aronov et al. for MA would appear [1], if there were any present in the sample. However, the mass spectrum of MA shown in Figure S7 does not present neither strong nor unambiguous evidence for the presence of this photoinduced trimer species. The strong peak at $m/z = 120$ (see Figure S7), which would correspond to a loss of the ester (OCH_3) unit in MA, points towards a potential photofragmentation process taking place in MA. However, given the previously reported mass spectrum of MA [2], which also shows a strong peak at $m/z = 120$, it is not possible to firmly assign this fragment to photodegradation, as it could also be the result of the electrospray ionization process. It is also possible that there could be smaller fragments that are outside of the m/z range of detection of these experiments. Nevertheless, while we are unable to identify the photoproduct generated through photodegradation of MA, this photodegradation is unambiguously evidenced by the strong color change observed for mixture A (see main manuscript).

Figure S7. Mass spectrum obtained for mixture A (containing only MA) post-irradiation.

In the mass spectrum of EHMC, shown in Figure S8, we see not only the parent peak ($m/z = 292$), but also a small contribution from EHMC dimers, visible at $m/z = 581$. This confirms the [2+2] photocycloadditions that have been reported to take place between two molecules of EHMC at high concentrations [3]. Apart from that, we see also the peaks corresponding to SCHERCEMOL™ LL, as discussed above, and lower m/z peaks corresponding to fragments of EHMC, generated by either irradiation or electrospray ionization. It is worth recalling that the main process taking place in irradiated EHMC is photoisomerization, which is undetectable by mass spectrometry.

Importantly, the mass spectra of mixture C, shown in Figure 9, contains no other dominant peaks: as expected, the peaks corresponding to MA, EHMC and SCHERCEMOL™ LL are still present, but there is no evidence of a [2+2] photocycloaddition taking place between MA and EHMC, as it does between EHMC and avobenzone [4]. In addition to these mass spectrometry results, the strong color change brought about by the photodegradation of MA (see main manuscript) is no longer observed when EHMC is added to the mixture, suggesting that EHMC is not only an effective quencher of MA's triplet states (as had already been suggested by Kikuchi) [5], but this quenching does not seem to lead to any further (potentially harmful) chemistry. It can be concluded that the combination of MA and EHMC does not lead to the generation of photoproducts resulting from their interaction.

Line#:1 R.Time:----(Scan#:----)
MassPeaks:19
Spectrum Mode:Averaged 0.133-0.400(9-25) Base Peak:291.15(12106687)
BG Mode:Calc Segment 1 - Event 1
Q3 Scan : CE:

Mixture B
(Chromatogram: 23F21.003)

Figure S8. Mass spectrum obtained for mixture B (containing only EHMC) post-irradiation.

Line#:1 R.Time:----(Scan#:----)
MassPeaks:13
Spectrum Mode:Averaged 0.133-0.517(9-32) Base Peak:152.00(13821146)
BG Mode:Calc Segment 1 - Event 1
Q3 Scan : CE:

Mixture C
(Chromatogram: 23F21.003)

Figure S9. Mass spectrum obtained for mixture C (containing MA and EHMC) post-irradiation.

References

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